

Comedy at War – Eupolis of Athens

Everyone has heard of the Athenian comic dramatist Aristophanes (c.446-386 BCE). His plays *Frogs*, *Wasps*, *Clouds* and others remain the most well known of ancient Comedies. In his plays, he launched scathing attacks on prominent figures in Athens at the time, mostly during the Peloponnesian War (431-404 BCE). What is less common knowledge, however, is that he was only one of an entire movement known as Old Comedy, active during the war. The three masters of Athenian Old Comedy were acknowledged as Aristophanes, Cratinus and Eupolis and tantalising details of the latter's life and plays open up remarkable possibilities for the role of comedy during the Peloponnesian War.

Old Comedy

We know relatively little of the lives of many of the authors of Old Comedy and Cratinus and Eupolis are no exception. They, along with the other writers of Old Comedy exist only in fragments or *testimonia* and no full plays survive. Even for Aristophanes, only eleven of his forty plays survive. Unsurprisingly then, Aristophanes dominates Old Comedy for us, Cratinus has come to take second place whilst Eupolis has been relegated to a distant third. There are many other authors of comic plays (almost sixty) who we know from surviving lists of victors at the *Dionysia* and *Lenaia* festivals, the two dramatic festivals on the Attic calendar. There are, however, remarkable insights to be found in even the briefest of anecdotes in regard to these other authors. We do have a list of victories for Cratinus and Eupolis (whose record of seven prizes, four at the *Dionysia* and three in the *Lenaia* in only fourteen or fifteen plays is a remarkable strike rate; four of his seven plays submitted for the *Dionysia* won). Cratinus' career was long, his first play coming in around 454 and his last in 423. In that career of approximately 24 plays he achieved nine victories. Aristophanes won much less often with perhaps only two victories at the *Dionysia* (*Babylonioi* may have won in 426 and he won again in 387) and three at the *Lenaia* (*Acharnians*, *Knights* and *Frogs*). Yet we know some of his plays came second at the *Dionysia* (*Wasps*, *Peace*, and *Birds*), and *Clouds* came third. Ian Storey compares Aristophanes with Steven Spielberg, a great artist ignored by the establishment of his day. Plato certainly uses him as the key representative of Comedy in his dialogues the *Apology* and the *Symposium*. The question then is how Aristophanes came to be regarded as the greatest exponent of Old Comedy, but that is not one not to be answered here!

The *Dionysia* and the *Lenaia*

The *Great* or *City Dionysia* Festival was held each year in Athens from the late 6th century (legend has the first play by Thespis in 534 BCE) to honour the god Dionysus with theatrical performances. It was held in the month of *Elaphebolion* (corresponding to March-April), perhaps to celebrate the end of winter or the harvest. Plays were produced at the 10,000 seat Theatre of Dionysus and the authors competed to be judged the best poet (each would submit three tragedies and a Satyr play, a bawdy satire). The earliest surviving tragedy is Aeschylus' *Persae* from 472 and the only Satyr play to survive complete is Euripides' *Cyclops* from 408 (or earlier). In 487 or 486 Comedy was introduced into the *Dionysia* and five comic poets would compete for the prize of best comic poet by submitting a play. A poet could not submit tragedies and Satyr play in the same year as a comedy. In around 440, the *Lenaia*, or *Minor* Festival of Dionysius, held in the month of *Gamelion* (January-February), introduced a competition for comedy only although a tragedy competition was added in 432 (but not one for satyr plays). The festival was originally held in the *Lenaion*, a theatre outside the Agora, but then moved to the Theatre of Dionysus although when is unclear.

'Everyone knows Eupolis'

We have details of Aristophanes' plays and his attacks on individuals during the war such as the demagogue Athenian general Cleon (the whole of *Knights*, *Acharnians* lines 377-82, 502-505, 659-60 and *Wasps* lines 1284-1291). Given Aristophanes large output, however, these attacks represent a relatively small aspect of his work. The one author for which the political and military aspects of the Peloponnesian War made up the main thrust of his work is Eupolis. And it is Eupolis who seems to have been the 'first' of the authors of Old Comedy, considered superior to Aristophanes and Cratinus by Horace (*Satire* 1.4.1-5) and Macrobius (*Saturnalia* 7.5.8) who claims 'everyone knows Eupolis.' This is despite the fact that no Eupolis play survives complete and we can only garner information from fragments and *testimonia*. A marble bust of Eupolis was discovered in 1998 in the courtyard of the house of parliament in Athens. Despite this frustratingly incomplete portrait, what emerges is the picture of the vast majority of his plays concerning themselves with the political and military milieu. We should bear in mind that Eupolis' entire career took place during the Peloponnesian War (429-412) and thus not be surprised at the overwhelming political and military nature of his comedies.

A marble bust of Eupolis, excavated in the courtyard of Parliament house, Athens, in February 1998.

As far as we can tell, he conforms to the idea found in Aristophanes, that he was educating the audience through his plays. Eupolis had fourteen or fifteen plays produced in this seventeen-year span (probably equally divided between the *Dionysia* and the *Lenaia*) and we know that he was on active military service during some of the other years.

The *Suda* ε 3657 tells us that Eupolis' first play was produced when he was seventeen, giving us a birth date of 447/6 since another passage tells us that that play was produced in the archonship of Apollodorus (430/429). The *Suda* passage also tells us that Eupolis 'died in a shipwreck in the Hellespont during the Peloponnesian War. As a result, poets were forbidden to serve in the military.' The context of this passage is most usually assumed to be the naval battle of Cynossema in 411 (Thucydides 8.99-109) although it could have been Arginusae (406) or Aegospotami (405). The name Eupolis does occur on a list of naval casualties for c. 411 (*IG* i³.1190.52) but we should be wary of identifying that name with 'our' Eupolis as the name was not uncommon. No play or any other evidence can be dated to after c.410 and so 411 is most commonly accepted as the date of his death. In the *Autolycus* (Fr. 49) is the line 'I already hate Aristarchus as general' and Aristarchus was known to be general in 411.

There are, however, four seemingly differing traditions regarding Eupolis' death, several of which offer intriguing insights into the Peloponnesian War. The first names his death in the Hellespont. There are others which place his death and grave in Aegina (Aelian *On the Nature of Animals* 10.41) and Pausanias (2.7.3) states his tomb was in Sikyon. The Alcmaeonid family were also associated with Sikyon and Aristophanes may have been associated with Aegina (*Acharnians* lines 652-654). The other tradition is by far the most widespread: that Alcibiades drowned Eupolis on the way to Sicily in 415 as revenge for the attacks the poet had made on him his play *Baptai/The Dyers* (Juvenal 2.92, Aelius Aristides 3.8, Themistios 8.110, Platonios *On the Distinctions Among Comedians* 1.21-3, and others). What this suggests, of course, is that Eupolis was involved in the military forces involved in the Sicilian Expedition (and we have no play suggested for Eupolis in 414 or 413). Cicero (*Ad Atticum* 6.1.18) observed that Eratosthenes had already pointed out that Eupolis had had plays produced after the Sicilian expedition and so he cannot have been drowned on the way there. That does not mean he wasn't 'punished' by Alcibiades by a dunking in the sea on the journey over to Sicily.

Unfortunately, the fragments which survive of *The Dyers* don't allow too much to be made of how savage the attack on Alcibiades was (he may have been attacked in *Spongers* as well (Fr. 171)). Some have assumed that the whole play was an attack on him but this doesn't seem to be the case; perhaps it was simply a memorable scene. The *testimonia* tell us that the play portrayed immoral (especially effeminate) and (perhaps) uneducated men. It was considered savage enough, however, for the tradition of Alcibiades' revenge to grow up around it despite its obvious chronological problems.

There is enough in the surviving fragments and *testimonia* to establish that Eupolis was overwhelmingly concerned with the political and military conduct of the war. In fact, he seems to have been even more political than Aristophanes, whose attacks on Cleon and Socrates and others are well known. (Eupolis does call Socrates a 'babbling beggar' (fragment 386) although which play it might come from is unclear). In Galen's work *On My Own Books* (17) he states that he had a three volume set on political terms in Eupolis and another, five volume set, on political terms in Aristophanes. If Eupolis' fourteen or fifteen plays could fill three volumes but Aristophanes' forty plays only filled five, the more prominent political nature of Eupolis' output is clear. Indeed, Alcibiades' revenge is associated with moves to restrict such attacks in comedy as can be seen in Cleon's possible prosecution of Aristophanes (although it may refer to Callistratus, *Acharnians* lines 377-382). In *Cities* (Fr. 220) Eupolis mentions Syracosius who is supposed to have proposed a bill

against personal comedy (*Birds* line 1297). Even from the fragments we know Eupolis targeted, not only Alcibiades, but other prominent individuals such as Callias, Phormion and Hyperbolus, and many more besides.

Eupolis' other plays, where we can tell, seem to be quite pointed in their political and military content. His most famous play, *Demoi/Demes*, had four great Athenian leaders brought back from the dead (perhaps as ghosts) to improve the situation at Athens. These were Pericles, Miltiades, Solon and Aristides. *Demes* was the most cited play in the ancient world and in 1911 a papyrus from the Cairo codex (F 99) with 120 lines was published. The date of the play is tricky but, overwhelmingly, it is dated to 412, after the disastrous defeat of the Sicilian Expedition in 413 and a suitable time when Athens would need 'saving'. Storey, however, dates the play to 417 because of a mention of the Mantinea campaign (F 99 30-32) and perhaps allusion to Hyperbolus who was ostracized in 416. There is a clear indication that the quality of generalship had been allowed to slip. Eupolis (Fr. 103) claims the current young generals had slept their way to the top and he has Miltiades swear on 'his' battle of Marathon not to 'let them get away with it' (Fr. 106). Miltiades' generalship is presented as the best Athens had ever seen (Fr. 130) (Aristophanes too praises Marathon – *Wasps* lines 1075-1101 and *Acharnians* lines 692-700). Themistocles, by contrast (Fr. 126) 'was clever, but couldn't control his hand.' In an unassigned Eupolis fragment, we have another statement showing this as a clear concern during the war (Fr. 384):

'This is not how we old men used to live. Our city had generals from the greatest families, leaders in wealth and birth, to whom we prayed as if they were gods – and gods they were to us. And so we lived in security. But now we take the field in haphazard fashion, electing as our generals the scum of the earth.'

Other plays by Eupolis' were also clearly military in theme (even when surviving fragments do not allow us to make much of them) – *Draft-Dodgers*, *Helots*, *Spongers*, (which may be the context of the attack on Socrates), *Officers*. Just as with *The Dyers*, commentators have often confidently assigned a date to these plays based on events in the war when there is nothing sure in the evidence to support such a date. That said, the surviving fragments clearly have a contemporary war-time meaning. Another unassigned fragment (Fr. 394) has 'seeing the flashing Lambdas he was terrified,' referring to the device on Spartan hoplite shields. *Draft Dodgers* has Peisander described as 'the most cowardly soldier in the army' (Fr. 35) and it seems as if Phormion may have been targeted in that play as well. In *Friends* (Fr. 293) we find 'You weren't very smart, old man, to accept this cavalry subsidy so quickly before learning how to ride,' showing a clear concern over charlatans

within the Athenian military system and inappropriate candidates taking up certain political and military positions.

In his *Marikas*, dated relatively securely to the *Lenaiia* of 421, Eupolis attacked the demagogue Hyperbolus. Nicias is accused of treason too (Fr. 193). The play is more notorious because it followed Aristophanes' *Knights* and in the revised *Clouds* (lines 551-559), Aristophanes accuses Eupolis of plagiarism, 'turning our *Knights* inside out,' and thus it represents the idea of a 'war between the poets.' In *The Dyers* (Fr. 89) Eupolis claimed he and Aristophanes collaborated together on *Knights*. There are similarities between the two but enough differences that we don't need to take Aristophanes at his word.

Eupolis' *Cities* seems to pit Athens against those allied cities who opposed her imperial ambitions. It again references the heritage of Marathon (Fr. 237) and we have reference to Chios as an ally of Athens who sends ships and is obedient (Fr. 246). Chios revolted from Athens in 412. Other subject allies are described as full of 'scorpions and informers' (Tenos, Fr. 245) and Cyzicus is 'full of staters' (Fr. 247).

In *Officers*, the god Dionysus joins the Athenian navy, and, as with all Dionysus comedies, we therefore find the god in an incongruous situation. He encounters a harsh taskmaster in the Athenian admiral Phormion who was prominent in the early years of the war, especially at the victories of Naupactus in 429/8. Dionysus makes all kinds of errors, dresses inappropriately (Fr. 272-3) and fails to learn to row properly (Fr. 268.51-55). All these comic situations probably make comment on the 'actual' situation in the navy and we may be able to link the play with Eupolis' own service (he may have served in the navy from the Sicilian expedition to at least 211). The play is usually dated to 415 and thus may be an anti-war play and a comment on the kinds of inappropriate men being recruited into the navy in the build up to the Sicilian expedition. What is more, they may be the kinds of practices Eupolis had seen first-hand prior to his dunking at the hands of Alcibiades. If the play is to be read in this way, we can see parallels in Aristophanes' treatment of Lamachus in the *Acharnians* (lines 566-625, 1071-1142, and 1174-1226). Phormion isn't mentioned in Thucydides after 428 (3.7.1) but is mentioned elsewhere as late as 411 (*Lysistrata* line 804). Storey considers that the play should be dated to 415 and regraded as a kind of 'Dionysus goes to Sicily' political comedy. Phormion here might be considered in the same vein as the great generals of time-gone-by we see in *Demes*, another reminder of how things should be done and

how they were done in the past. A statue of Phormion was erected on the Acropolis, acknowledging that the city recognised its debt to him.

Eupolis therefore seems to have been an active member of the Athenian navy and a comic poet greatly concerned with the conduct of the war both politically and militarily. If the *Suda* is correct and poets were exempted from military service after Eupolis' death, then his loss may have been keenly felt. His, and Aristophanes, use of comedy during war-time to criticize and turn the spotlight on to the conduct of a war can be seen to have successors in the comedy of Charlie Chaplin (1940's *The Great Dictator*) as well as during the Vietnam War, the Gulf War and more recent conflicts.

Further Reading

Ian C. Storey *Eupolis, Poet of Old Comedy* (Oxford, 2003).

David Harvey & John Wilkins (eds) *The Rivals of Aristophanes* (London, 2000).

Ian C. Storey *Fragments of Old Comedy*, 3 Volumes, (Cambridge, Massachusetts, 2011).